

Toughness and strength of Cordierite glass ceramic- Silicon Nitride whisker composites

Robert F. Cook
Winterville, NC 28590 USA
robertfcook@mac.com

The toughness and strength of a series of glass ceramic-whisker composites are investigated in an extensive series of indentation fracture based tests. The tests include measurements of hardness from indentation deformation, measurements of relative toughness in air from indentation crack lengths and *in situ* measurements of crack extension in stressed specimens, and measurements of toughness and assessments of flaw size from inert indentation- and intrinsic-strength tests. The extensive tests illustrate the power of indentation techniques to evaluate the fracture properties of structural ceramics at small length scales. In the case here, whisker addition led to significant increases in composite toughness, from 1.4 MPa m^{1/2} to 2.6 MPa m^{1/2}, and increases in intrinsic flaw size, such that composite strength remained invariant at approximately 250 MPa.

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1. Introduction

Development and application of advanced structural ceramics requires knowledge of mechanical properties of ceramic materials and of the load-bearing capacity of ceramic components. In particular, ceramics are typically brittle and fail by crack propagation with little accompanying plastic deformation—measurement of toughness and fracture strength are thus required for structural ceramic design and development. As fracture strengths of structural ceramics are typically controlled by cracking from small, microscopic flaws, toughness at short crack lengths and distributions of flaw sizes are critical mechanical properties for comparing materials and predicting component performance. Controlled-flaw indentation techniques are ideally suited for evaluating these properties and many other small-scale fracture and deformation phenomena [Lawn and Cook, 2012; Marshall *et al.*, 2015]. The basis of such techniques is the controlled loading and unloading of a sharp indenter onto a ceramic surface to form a residual contact impression and cracks. Early works in this area showed that measurements of indentation crack lengths or measurements of strengths of components containing strength-controlling indentation flaws could be used to estimate toughness [Anstis *et al.*, 1981; Chantikul *et al.*, 1981] and, when the measurements were combined, estimate intrinsic flaw sizes [Lawn *et al.*, 1980]. The subsequent advances in fracture properties evaluation based on these techniques are summarized in overview works considering the now pervasive method of indentation crack length measurements in air [Cook, 2020a] and sophisticated indentation-strength methods that enable quantification of multi-scale effects in fracture, including contact damage, material microstructure, and environmental reaction kinetics [Cook, 2015].

Further advances in ceramic toughness, strength, and flaw size determination are enabled by recent works of experimental fracture measurement in two areas. The first fracture measurement takes advantage of indentation techniques and enables direct assessment of variations in toughness with crack length [Braun *et al.*, 1992; Kovar *et al.*, 2000]. The measurement is based on *in situ* observations of crack propagation during indentation strength tests. (*Ex situ* crack propagation measurements have also been implemented but do not provide a complete assessment of toughness variation [Cook and Lawn, 1983; Cook, 2020b].) The second fracture measurement implements probabilistic methods and enables direct assessment of flaw size distributions [Cook and DelRio, 2019ab]. The measurement makes distinction between a population of flaws and a sampled distribution and has been applied to machining flaws, indentation flaws, and pores in bulk ceramics, to ceramic particles [Cook, 2020c], and to silicon microelectromechanical systems components [Cook *et al.*, 2019; DelRio *et al.*, 2020].

The work here will apply the above two more recent techniques in a comprehensive set of fracture measurements on an advanced structural ceramic, a composite of cordierite glass-

ceramic reinforced with silicon nitride whiskers. Specifically, a group of microstructural variants of the ceramic composite with different whisker contents will be examined using both the earlier indentation crack length and strength measurement techniques and the more recent toughness variation and flaw size distribution measurement techniques. The work begins with a description of the experimental methods, emphasizing materials characterization and indentation-based testing and provides background observations in these areas. This is followed by a summary of the required analysis methods, including indentation fracture mechanics and the probabilistic failure framework. For both the experimental and analysis methods extensive details are given in the works cited above and the focus in the sections here is to enable measurement interpretation. The results follow, considering toughness measurements and strength measurements. The aim of the work here is not to find the “best” composite, but to demonstrate how a comprehensive set of measurements can be used to guide advanced structural ceramic development and application.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Materials

The glass-ceramic composites were formed from tapecast greensheets [Tummala, 1991; Knickerbocker, 1992; Knickerbocker *et al.*, 1993] that contained cordierite glass powder and up to 35 % by relative volume (vol%) $1\ \mu\text{m} \times 10\ \mu\text{m}$ β -phase Si_3N_4 whiskers (Ube Industries Ltd, Ube City, Japan [Homeny *et al.*, 1990]), along with binders and dispersants. The volume fractions, V_f , of whiskers were determined relative to densified 0 % “blank” glass-ceramic and analyses here predominantly focused on $V_f = 0\%$, 5 %, 10 %, and 15 % materials. Figure 1(a) shows a group of whiskers and the glass particles of a greensheet. During mixing of the glass, whiskers, binder, and dispersant the initially longer whiskers were broken down to their 10 μm length. On tape casting, there was some preferential alignment of the whiskers parallel to the greensheet faces, as shown in the cross-section of a fractured greensheet, Fig. 1(b). The porosity of the green sheet is visible in both Figs. 1(a) and (b). The 150 μm thick greensheets were laminated, free-sintered and then diced to produce 5.5 mm \times 7.0 mm \times 55 mm bars, or punched before sintering to produce 28.6 mm \times 2.3 mm discs. The edges of the bars were chamfered and polished and the surfaces of the discs were polished. All compositions underwent identical sintering and polishing treatments.

The density of the sintered composites was measured using the Archimedes’ displacement technique on several bars of each composition. Comparisons with the theoretical densities revealed that the addition of whiskers significantly reduced the relative densities, ρ_r , of the

sintered glass-ceramic composites such that there were significant volume fractions of porosity, $V_p = (1 - \rho_r)$. The variation of ρ_r with V_f is shown in Fig. 2. The uncertainty in relative density measurement was approximately 0.1 % and is smaller than the symbol size. The mean values of ρ_r are given in Table 1. The nature of the porosity in the sintered composites was assessed using mercury porosimetry measurements. For materials with $V_f < 10$ %, the open porosity was < 0.3 % (compared with total porosity $V_p = 6.3$ % for the $V_f = 10$ % material), whereas for $V_f = 15$ %, the open porosity was 7.3 % (compared with $V_p = 14.7$ %). These measurements suggest a change in the microstructure from a porous solid to an open foam in the range $10 \% < V_f < 15$ %.

Figure 1. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of (a) a group of Si₃N₄ whiskers imbedded in the cordierite glass particles of a composite green sheet and (b) a cross-section of a fractured greensheet showing the partial alignment of the whiskers.

Figure 2. Plot of relative density of sintered composites as a function of volume fraction of Si_3N_4 whiskers added to cordierite glass-ceramic. The whiskers clearly retard densification.

Fracture cross-sections of sintered specimens with $V_f = 5\%$ and $V_f = 15\%$ are shown in Fig. 3 (the same magnification is used for both specimens). The image of the $V_f = 5\%$ material, Fig. 3(a), shows porosity at two different scales. At the smaller scale, near spherical (circular in section) isolated pores, approximately $1\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, are distributed throughout the material and are referred to here as “micropores.” Such micropores are typical in the closed porosity microstructures that develop during final stage sintering of monolithic ceramics and constitute the majority of the porosity. At the larger scale, a single lenticular (elliptical in section) pore, approximately $30\ \mu\text{m}$ in length, is shown. The pore contains a cluster of entangled whiskers and very little sintered glass-ceramic, and is referred to here as a “macropore.” Such macropores are a consequence of incomplete mixing of constituents in the green state and persist throughout sintering of composites. Although large, such macropores constitute a minority of sintered material porosity and, as is typical, were observed here to be distributed sparsely throughout the composites. Macropores were observed more frequently here in the materials with greater whisker volume fractions.

Figure 3. SEM images of fracture cross sections of sintered cordierite glass ceramic-silicon nitride whisker composites. (a) $V_f = 5\%$ volume fraction of whiskers, (b) $V_f = 15\%$.

The image of the $V_f = 15\%$ material, Fig. 3(b), differs from Fig. 3(a) in several ways. First, the fracture surface is much more rough in the $V_f = 15\%$ material. Second, the distributed porosity (dark regions) in this material is angular and irregular in shape, much more pervasive, and larger, up to $5\ \mu\text{m}$ in size, than the micropores in Fig. 3(a). Such porosity, comparable in scale to the densified glass-ceramic regions, is typical of the open porosity microstructures that develop during early stage or arrested sintering of monolithic ceramics. Close inspection of the densified regions in Fig. 3(b) reveals cross sections of very small isolated spherical pores and broken whiskers (small bright discs, also visible in Fig. 3(a)). Nevertheless, the implication from Fig. 3(b) is that the irregular porosity is open and constitutes the majority, leading to the rough fracture surface. Clearly the whiskers retarded densification of the composite by both inhibiting the viscous sintering process [Knickerbocker *et al.*, 1993] where the whiskers were homogeneously distributed and by forming undensifiable agglomerates where heterogeneously distributed.

Figure 4. SEM images of isolated macropores in cordierite glass ceramic-silicon nitride whisker composites. (a) $V_f = 5\%$ volume fraction of whiskers, (b) $V_f = 15\%$.

Magnified views of macropores in $V_f = 5\%$ and $V_f = 15\%$ composites are shown in Fig. 4 (the 5% specimen is that from Fig. 3(a); the same magnification is used for both specimens). In both images, the macropores contain almost no glass ceramic particles and consist of entangled whisker agglomerates with many whiskers perpendicular to the greensheet tapecasting and lamination directions (horizontal in the images). The macropore in the $V_f = 15\%$ material, Fig. 4(b), is larger than that in the $V_f = 5\%$ material, Fig. 4(a). The observations of Figs. 3 and 4 were typical of many images examined for the composites.

Young's modulus E was determined from the load-displacement responses of small bars 1.0 mm \times 5.0 mm \times 35 mm cut from the larger test bars. A stiff, three-point bend fixture under displacement control, instrumented with a resistance displacement gauge and a resistance load-cell were used to measure the responses. The values of E are given in Table 1. The uncertainties reflect test and between-specimen variability. E was slightly greater for the 5% and 10% compositions than that of the blank 0% glass-ceramic, but significantly less for the 15% composition. Typical values of the Young's moduli for dense cordierite glass ceramic and silicon nitride are 121 GPa and 300 GPa, respectively. These values and the observations of Figs. 3 and 4 imply that there were competing influences of stiffer whiskers and compliant porous glass ceramic regions in determining the moduli of the composites. The initial increase in modulus at small V_f implies good bonding between at least some of the whiskers and the glass-ceramic matrix before a decrease in modulus at large V_f associated with porosity.

2.2. Contact properties

A Vickers diamond pyramid indenter was used for all indentation tests in this study. The indentation load-displacement, P - h , behavior of the composite materials was determined using an instrumented indenter with capacitance displacement gauges and resistance load cell [Cook and Pharr, 1990; Thurn *et al.*, 2002]. Polished discs of material were indented to a peak depth of 20 μm at a penetration rate of 1 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and the resulting P - h data recorded. Complete indentation cycles are shown in Fig. 5. The open symbols are data for the designated material; the response of the blank glass-ceramic is shown as the repeated solid lines and provides a reference.

The load-displacement behavior of the composites was typical of that for ceramics: combined elastic and plastic deformation during loading (leading to a quadratic dependence of P on h); elastic recovery during unloading (leaving a remnant displacement and contact impression). Comparison of the composite indentation responses with that of the blank glass-ceramic shows that addition of the whiskers (with the concomitant increase in porosity) leads to smaller sustained peak loads at peak displacement and larger remnant displacements. That is, the composites were less contact resistant and exhibited greater irreversible deformation relative to

reversible deformation during contact. An indication of the relative amounts of irreversible and reversible deformation during contact is the coefficient of restitution e , which gives a measure of the prospective relative rebound velocity of an impacting particle [Tabor, 1951]. The value of e may be calculated from the load-displacement data by $e = (U_r/U)^{1/2}$, where U is the total amount of energy expended by the indenter during the loading cycle and U_r is the amount of energy recovered during the unloading cycle, represented by the areas under the upper and lower $P-h$ curves, respectively. The values of e are given Table 1 and indicate that the addition of whiskers significantly decreased e , implying that small particle impacts would be more likely to generate deformation damage in a composite surface relative to a blank glass-ceramic surface. The likely mechanism for the decrease in e is enhanced pore collapse and crushing of whisker entanglements during contact of composites. The smooth responses in Fig. 5 imply that the 20 μm indentation depth sampled many pores [Cook, 2018a], consistent with Fig. 3.

Figure 5. Indentation load-displacement plots for cordierite glass-ceramics containing Si_3N_4 whiskers. The symbols represent individual load-displacement measurements and the solid lines represents the response of the blank material. Data shown are every second point for single replicated cycles.

Figure 6. Vickers indentation flaws. (a) Schematic plan diagram. Optical micrographs of 100 N indentations in (b) blank cordierite glass-ceramic and (c) glass-ceramic containing 15 vol% Si_3N_4 whiskers. The smaller contact impression but more extensive cracks indicate that the blank glass-ceramic is harder but less tough than the composite.

Figure 6(a) is a schematic plan diagram of a Vickers indentation flaw. The central square is the residual contact impression indicating remnant plastic deformation, with depth formed as in Fig. 5. The residual impression semi-diagonal is the dimension a indicated. Figures 6(b) and 6(c) show optical micrographs of indentations in the blank glass-ceramic and 15 vol % whisker composite, respectively. Both indentations were formed with a peak load of $P = 100$ N. In both micrographs the square contact impression is evident, and, as expected from the indentation load-displacement tests, the remnant impression in the composite is larger implying a smaller contact resistance. A measure of contact resistance is the mean contact pressure associated with plastic deformation, the hardness H , defined by [Tabor, 1951]

$$H = P/2a^2. \quad (1)$$

Inverting this equation gives

$$a = (1/2H)^{1/2}P^{1/2}, \quad (2)$$

showing that the indentation impression dimension a should increase as $P^{1/2}$ in a material of constant hardness.

Figure 7. Plots of the indentation half-penny crack length and contact impression dimension as a function of indentation load for cordierite glass-ceramics containing silicon nitride whiskers. The solid lines are best fits to the data consistent with constant hardness and toughness, Eqs. (2) and (4).

Indentations were made on the polished discs in the load range $P = 2 \text{ N}$ to 300 N and the resulting contact impressions measured by optical microscopy. The results are shown in Fig. 7. Individual symbols represent the means of eight measurements at each load (uncertainty is smaller than the symbol size) and the lower solid lines are slope-1/2 best fits to the impression data consistent with Eq. (2). Over the load domain tested all materials were described by constant hardness and the values are given in Table 1. (Here and following, values are given as means and standard deviations of experimental measurements, using propagation of variance as required.) Hardness decreased significantly on whisker addition and the decrease is probably explained by the same pore collapse mechanism suggested for the decreasing coefficient of restitution. The values are consistent with the idea that the variation of hardness with whisker volume fraction is almost completely dominated by material porosity.

The micrograph of the indentation in the blank glass-ceramic, Fig. 6(b), shows the two dominant crack systems generated at sharp contacts [Cook and Pharr, 1990]. Surface traces of cracks are visible emanating from the contact impression corners. These cracks propagate perpendicular to the material surface and control the maximum stress—the strength—sustainable by the indentation [Chantikul *et al.*, 1981]. Opposing surface traces most likely reflect a single crack system that is connected beneath the impression to a form a semi-circular half-penny crack, although at small loads this morphology is less common and indentations are typified by less connected surface localized radial cracks. The curved traces and surfaces of lateral cracks are visible emanating from the contact impression edges. These cracks propagate approximately parallel to the material surface and are responsible for material removal—chipping—at the contact and exert a secondary influence on strength by modifying the indentation residual stress field [Cook and Roach, 1986; Cook, 2015].

The whisker composites exhibited a greater resistance to both half-penny and lateral cracking at contacts, as shown in the micrograph of Fig. 6(b). Both indentation crack initiation (whether a crack forms at a contact or not) and indentation cracking susceptibility (how long cracks are) were impeded in the composites. The increased resistance to indentation cracking was determined by measuring the lengths of surface traces of half-penny cracks c (from the contact impression center) as a function of indentation load P over the load range 2 N to 300 N . The results are shown in Fig. 7, noting that cracks were not observable in the 15% composite at small indentation loads as a consequence of suppressed crack initiation. Individual symbols are the means of eight measurements at each load (uncertainty is smaller than the symbols size). Indentation cracking susceptibility is quantified by recognizing that the stress-intensity factor (SIF) K acting on the indentation half-penny cracks is given by

$$K = \chi P/c^{3/2}, \quad (3)$$

where χ is a dimensionless load-invariant factor. The equilibrium condition for the indentation cracks is $K = T_{\text{air}}$, where T_{air} is the toughness of the material in air. Imposing this equilibrium condition and inverting Eq. (3) gives [Cook, 2020]

$$c_{\text{air}} = BP^{2/3}, \quad (4)$$

where B is the cracking susceptibility. Equation (4) shows that the equilibrium indentation crack length c_{air} should increase as $P^{2/3}$ in a material of constant toughness, noting that the experimental measurable $B = (T_{\text{air}}/\chi)^{-2/3}$. More details are given below and in the Analysis section. The parallel construction of Eqs. (1)-(2) and (3)-(4) is noted.

The upper solid lines in Fig. 7 are slope-2/3 best fits to the crack length data consistent with Eq. (4). Over the load domain tested all materials were described by constant cracking susceptibility and the values are given in Table 1. The composites exhibited smaller values of B , consistent with greater, microstructure-invariant values of T/χ . To further investigate fracture behavior, the dependence of χ on the elastic and plastic properties of an indented material must be considered. χ is a dimensionless, material-dependent parameter characterizing the intensity of the residual stress field acting on indentation cracks. The residual field arises from the strain mismatch between the remnant plastic contact impression and the surrounding elastic matrix [Lawn and Cook, 2012]. The material dependence of χ is given by

$$\chi = \xi(E/H)^{1/2}, \quad (5)$$

where ξ is a dimensionless geometry term that is invariant for ideal indentations. Combining Eq. (5) into the expression for B gives

$$T_{\text{air}} = \xi(E/H)^{1/2}B^{-3/2}, \quad (6)$$

which permits an absolute estimate of T_{air} [Anstis *et al.*, 1981; Cook 2020a]. Of perhaps greater use here is a relative estimate that allows for comparison of microstructural effects and avoids explicit knowledge of ξ :

$$T_{\text{air}}/T_{\text{air}}^0 = [(E/H)^{1/2}B^{-3/2}]/[(E/H)^{1/2}B^{-3/2}]^0 \quad (7)$$

where X^0 indicates quantity X evaluated for the blank $V_f = 0\%$ material, noting that E , H , and B are given in Table 1.

Using Eq. (7), Fig. 8 plots $T_{\text{air}}/T_{\text{air}}^0$ along with H/H^0 , E/E^0 , and ρ_r as a function of V_f for the blank and composite materials. As guides to the eye: the shaded band indicates no change in property relative to the base material, consistent with the average uncertainty; the upper dashed line indicates rule of mixtures change in property of a factor of three between cordierite and silicon nitride end members. As discussed above, the relative modulus E/E^0 does not vary much as compliant porosity and stiff whiskers offset. Relative hardness H/H^0 decreases with increase in V_f at a greater rate than does relative density. This observation implies that the *mechanism* of plastic deformation at contacts is altered in the composites by the addition of whiskers and the

consequent porosity from that in dense cordierite glass-ceramic. As discussed, the tendency towards more foam-like deformation localized to the contact by pore collapse and crushing of whisker entanglements is most likely [Cook, 2018a]. Relative toughness $T_{\text{air}}/T_{\text{air}}^0$ increases at a greater rate with increase in V_f than does the rule of mixtures estimate. This observation implies that the *mechanism* of fracture is altered in the composites from that in dense cordierite glass-ceramic. In particular, the addition of the whiskers toughens the composites beyond any deleterious effects of the associated porosity. The toughening probably derives from cohesive bridging zones formed behind the tips of propagating cracks [Cook, 2015]. The zones are associated with whisker sliding and friction caused by crack opening displacements. This toughening mechanism is obviously not available to either monolithic cordierite or silicon nitride and hence the relative toughness exceeds a rule of mixtures estimate.

Figure 8. Plot of relative density and relative mechanical properties of cordierite glass ceramic composites as a function of silicon nitride whisker volume fraction. The resistance to localized plastic deformation measured by the relative hardness depends critically on porosity of the composites. Conversely, the resistance to fracture measured by relative toughness depends on whisker addition. Relative modulus is influenced by both and exhibits little variation.

Table 1. Bulk and contact properties of glass ceramic-whisker composites

Property	Volume fraction whiskers, V_f (%)						
	0	5	10	15	20	25	35
Relative density, ρ_r (%)	99.2	97.0	93.7	85.3	75.4	64.2	49.4
Young's modulus, E (GPa)	120 ± 10	136 ± 12	133 ± 11	104 ± 8			
Coefficient of restitution, e	0.82	0.80	0.77	0.70			
Hardness, H (GPa)	8.3 ± 0.5	8.2 ± 0.6	6.7 ± 0.8	3.1 ± 0.4			
Cracking susceptibility, B ($\mu\text{m N}^{-2/3}$)	13.4 ± 0.9	11.3 ± 0.7	11.1 ± 0.7	11.3 ± 0.5			

2.3. Toughness

Relative toughness and toughness variations can be estimated in greater detail from *in situ* observations of indentation crack extension under superimposed applied stress [Braun *et al.*, 1992; Kovar *et al.*, 2000]. During the application of stress, indentation half-penny cracks extend stably from their initial length to a final length at the onset of instability and failure. Monitoring this stable extension is an effective method of gauging the relative toughness of materials.

Bars of each composition were indented at their centers ($P = 100$ N) and loaded in a stiff four-bend bending fixture mounted on an optical microscope [Tandon and Cook, 1993; Hughey *et al.*, 2004]. Loading was controlled by a stepping motor and monitored by a resistance load cell, and the indentation crack extension measured optically. Applied stress σ_a was calculated from the bending load using standard beam theory. Care was taken to increment the load so that crack velocities averaged over a few load increments were $< 0.01 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and the system remained as close as possible to equilibrium. The experiments were performed in air so the toughness value was that appropriate to equilibrium in a moist environment, T_{air} . Two bars, four cracks, were measured for each composition except 15 %, for which one bar was measured.

2.4. Strength

Inert strength tests of specimens containing dominant indentation flaws were performed on the composites. Such tests carry many advantages: the flaw size can be pre-determined via the easily

controlled indentation load and a wide range of flaw sizes across the length scale of interest can be used; the geometry of the flaws is known from previous studies [Cook and Pharr, 1990] and the influence of lateral cracking in altering the flaw geometry detected in the strength response [Cook and Roach, 1986]; as strengths at a given flaw size can be compared between materials, toughness properties of materials can be compared [Chantikul *et al.*, 1981] and the variation of toughness with flaw size inferred from the strength response [Cook, 2015]; and finally, comparison with the intrinsic (unindented) strength can be used to infer the intrinsic flaw size [Lawn *et al.*, 1980].

Bar specimens were indented at their centers with the indentation diagonals aligned perpendicular to the bar axes. The specimens were then broken with the indented face in tension in a flexible four-point bend fixture (to prevent torque on the specimens). Rapid loading rates were used such that specimen failure occurred in ~ 50 ms and thus reactive species (primarily water vapor) were not able to access the crack tip during propagation to failure. The fixture was instrumented with a piezoelectric load cell and peak, failure, loads were recorded electronically. Failure stress was calculated from peak load using standard beam theory. Approximately five specimens were broken at each indentation load in the range $P = 2$ N to 300 N.

In order to gauge the intrinsic strengths, tests were performed on specimens containing no introduced indentation flaws. Polished disc specimens were used so that the failure distributions were representative of flaws intrinsic to the materials (and not an artifact of edge preparation). The discs were tested in biaxial flexure under inert conditions using a flat-on-three-ball test rig [Marshall, 1980] instrumented with the piezoelectric load cell. Strength was determined from peak load using standard plate theory. Approximately 50 specimens for each of the 5 %, 8 %, 10 %, and 15 % composites were tested and compared with 142 specimens of the blank 0 % material [Cook and DelRio, 2019b].

3. Analysis methods

The SIF arising from uniform stress σ_a applied to a crack of length c is

$$K = \psi \sigma_a c^{1/2}, \quad (8)$$

where ψ is a dimensionless, stress-invariant, geometrical factor. The net SIF acting on a stressed indentation half-penny crack is then the sum of Eqs. (3) and (8):

$$K = \chi P/c^{3/2} + \psi \sigma_a c^{1/2}. \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) is the basis for the toughness and strength analyses that follow, in both reactive (moist) air and inert environments.

3.1. Toughness variation

If the equilibrium condition $K = T_{\text{air}}$ is imposed for a crack in air loaded as described by Eq. (9), measurement of a $\sigma_a(c)$ trajectory for a specified P enables determination of material toughness variation $T_{\text{air}}(c)$ [Braun *et al.*, 1992; Kovar *et al.*, 2000] Such determination depends on knowledge of the geometrical factors χ and ψ . Evaluation of these factors to within a common multiplicative factor may be performed by an experiment on a material with single valued toughness (which does not need to be known numerically). Here the base glass ceramic was used for geometrical factor evaluation, assuming invariant toughness in air $T_{\text{air}} = T_{\text{air}}^0$ —an assumption supported here by Fig. 7. Imposing the equilibrium condition for this material and rearranging Eq. (9) gives

$$(\psi/T_{\text{air}}^0)\sigma_a c^{1/2} = 1 - (\chi/T_{\text{air}}^0)P/c^{3/2}. \quad (10)$$

Simple linear fitting of the experimental quantities $P/c^{3/2}$ and $\sigma_a c^{1/2}$ suggested by Eq. (10) thus provides the related calibration factors. Here $(\psi/T_{\text{air}}^0) = (1/1.12)$ and $(\chi/T_{\text{air}}^0) = (1/25.67)$ were determined, both with dimensions of $[\text{MPa m}^{1/2}]^{-1}$. For materials with crack geometry assumed identical to that of the calibration material, these factors enable determination of relative toughness $T_{\text{air}}/T_{\text{air}}^0$. Combining Eqs. (5) and (9) and imposing equilibrium gives

$$T_{\text{air}}/T_{\text{air}}^0 = (\psi/T_{\text{air}}^0)\sigma_a c^{1/2} + (\chi/\chi^0)(\chi/T_{\text{air}}^0)P/c^{3/2}, \quad (11)$$

where the relative residual stress term (χ/χ^0) is

$$(\chi/\chi^0) = (E/H)^{1/2}/(E^0/H^0)^{1/2}. \quad (12)$$

It is noted that Eq. (11) is an extension of Eq. (7) for non-zero applied stress and is identical to Eq. (7) for $\sigma_a = 0$.

3.2. Indentation strength variation

If the equilibrium condition $K = T_{\text{inert}}$ is imposed for a crack described by Eq. (9) in an inert environment, the maximum sustainable applied stress is

$$\sigma_m = 3T_{\text{inert}}^{4/3}/4^{4/3}\psi(\chi P)^{1/3}. \quad (13)$$

The stress σ_m is the strength of a component containing a dominant indentation flaw and thus depends on P . Equation (13) pertains for ideal indentations at moderate indentation loads and can be re-expressed similarly to Eq. (4) as

$$\sigma_m = SP^{-1/3}, \quad (14)$$

where S is an experimentally determined parameter with dimensions of $\text{MPa N}^{1/3}$. Equation (14) shows that the inert indentation strength σ_m should decrease as $P^{-1/3}$ in a material of constant

toughness, noting that the experimental measurable $S = 3(T_{\text{inert}}/4)^{4/3}/\psi\chi^{1/3}$. Combining Eq. (5) into the expression for S gives

$$T_{\text{inert}} = \eta(E/H)^{1/8}S^{3/4}, \quad (15)$$

permitting an absolute estimate of T_{inert} , where η is a dimensionless geometry term that is invariant for ideal indentations [Chantikul *et al.*, 1981]. Of perhaps greater use here is a relative estimate that allows comparison of microstructural effects and avoids explicit knowledge of η :

$$T_{\text{inert}}/T_{\text{inert}}^0 = [(E/H)^{1/8}S^{3/4}]/[(E/H)^{1/8}S^{3/4}]^0, \quad (16)$$

similar to Eqs. (7) and (11). At large indentation loads, lateral cracking as in Fig. 6 may relax χ thereby increasing the strength [Cook and Roach, 1986; Cook, 2015]—this effect was small here and is not considered in detail. At small indentation loads, flaws intrinsic to the material become dominant and strength controlling, leading to an upper bound on strength σ_f . The intrinsic flaws can be defined by a characteristic contact load P_f using Eq. (14)

$$\sigma_f = SP_f^{-1/3}. \quad (17)$$

The inert strength over the complete large-to-small indentation load domain (indentation-to-intrinsic strength range) can be described by a smooth p -norm function as in an earlier analysis [Cook, 2019b]. Using an empirical exponent $\alpha < -1$ to connect the strengths by

$$\sigma^\alpha = \sigma_m^\alpha + \sigma_f^\alpha \quad (18)$$

and combining Eqs. (14), (17), and (18) gives

$$\sigma = \sigma_f[1 + (P/P_f)^{-\alpha/3}]^{1/\alpha}. \quad (19)$$

Equation (19) describes the full experimental strength range, once the limiting experimental asymptotic values of S and σ_f are determined.

3.3. Intrinsic strength variation

The intrinsic strength data were analyzed as detailed in recent works considering strength variations and distributions of silicon components and nanowires, [Cook and DelRio, 2019a; Cook *et al.*, 2019], ceramics, [Cook and DelRio, 2019b], indentation crack lengths [Cook, 2020a] and particles [Cook, 2020c]. A brief account of application of the analysis is given here.

An empirical distribution function (edf) of intrinsic strengths, $Pr(\sigma)$, was formed for each material. The strengths were ranked from smallest to largest, $\sigma(i)$, where i is an index that spans the domain $i = 1$ to $i = N$, where N was the number of intrinsic strength measurements in the sample group for each material. The quantity $(i - 0.5)/N$ was formed for each index value and the discrete parametric function of the pairing $Pr(\sigma) = [\sigma(i), (i - 0.5)/N]$ formed the edf for each material. A smoothing function was fit visually to each edf by the continuous function

$H(\mu)$. The smoothing function is based on a non-linear perturbation of an incomplete Beta function [Cook and DelRio, 2019b] and is given by

$$H(\mu) = 30(\mu^{3p}/3 - \mu^{4p}/2 + \mu^{5p}/5), \quad (20a)$$

where μ is a relative strength parameter,

$$\mu = (\sigma - \sigma_{\min})/(\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}). \quad (20b)$$

Equation (20) describes a sigmoidal variation from 0 to 1 between empirical strength fitting bounds of σ_{\min} and σ_{\max} ; p is an empirical fitting factor of order unity controlling sigmoid symmetry. $H(\mu)$ is an estimator of the cumulative distribution function (cdf) of strengths $H(\sigma)$ set by the population of flaws, the sampling procedure, and the specimen size (for details see works cited above).

The strength-controlling intrinsic flaw distributions in the samples are determined from the strength measurements through specification of $\sigma(c)$. Here the Griffith relation,

$$\sigma = Dc^{-1/2} \quad (21)$$

was used, where D is a function of material fracture resistance and intrinsic crack geometry (D is similar to T/ψ). A key feature of Eq. (21) is that $d\sigma/dc < 0$, *i.e.*, strength decreases as flaw size increases. Other, more complicated, strength-flaw size relations could be selected (*e.g.*, related to cracks at pores [Chao and Shetty, 1992]), but all would be characterized by this negative derivative. As a consequence of the derivative, the sample crack length cdf, $H(c)$, is related to the sample strength cdf by $H(c) = 1 - H(\sigma)$. The crack length probability density function (pdf), $h(c)$, is related to the cdf by

$$h(c) = dH(c)/dc. \quad (22)$$

Determination of $h(c)$ for each material enables comparison of the strength controlling flaws, provided values for D are known. Here D/D^0 was taken to vary as $T_{\text{inert}}/T_{\text{inert}}^0$.

4. Results

4.1. Toughness measurements

Figure 9 shows the measured applied stress-crack length responses for indentation cracks in air for each composition. Symbols represent individual stress-crack length observations. The solid line represents the best fit to the blank glass-ceramic data as described by Eq. (10) and the stated geometrical factors and is reproduced for reference in each sub-plot. In all cases there was stable crack extension before failure. The stress to cause failure increased with whisker volume fraction and the stable extension, although less for the 5 % and 10 % materials, was considerably greater for the 15 % material. The enhanced failure stresses and increased extension are both indicative

of toughening. However, direct evidence of the ability of the whiskers to impede crack propagation was observed during stressing of the composites: frequently the crack tip would stop movement and become blocked at a whisker for many load increments before passing through or around the whisker and extending a considerable distance into the ceramic matrix in a single increment. Often these erratic crack-tip motions would be associated with discrete changes in the crack-opening displacement near whiskers behind the crack tip, supporting the idea that frictional interlocks behind the tip were influencing overall crack behavior. The “staircase” motion in the stress-extension responses of the composites indicates this erratic crack tip behavior. Observations on other sets of indentation cracks were similar.

Figure 9. Plots of equilibrium indentation crack length under the action of applied stress for glass-ceramic-silicon nitride whisker composites in air. All materials exhibit stable crack extension and the enhanced composite responses indicate whisker toughening.

Figure 10 is a plot of the relative toughness of the composite materials using the data from Fig. 9 and Eqs. (11) and (12). Although there is some scatter, it is clear that the toughness of the

composites is greater than that of the blank glass-ceramic and increases with increasing volume fraction of whiskers. It is also clear that the toughness does not increase dramatically for cracks longer than approximately 200 μm , consistent with the length scale for the onset of steady-state toughness estimated from the indentation-strength data, approximately 20–50 μm , Fig. 7. The relative toughness values are also consistent with those inferred from the indentation crack length data. The values determined from the direct long-crack measurements in Fig. 10 are 1.35 (5 % composite), 1.6 (10 %), and 1.9 (15 %), consistent with those from the static indentation short-crack measurements in Fig. 8.

Figure 10. Plot of relative toughness variation with crack length for glass-ceramic-silicon nitride whisker composites in air. Toughness increases significantly with whisker volume fraction (indicated) at long crack lengths and exhibits considerable scatter at short crack lengths.

4.2. Strength measurements

Figure 11 is a plot of inert indentation- and intrinsic-strengths of the materials. Open symbols represent individual indentation strength measurements and, as expected, decrease with increasing indentation load and flaw size. The dashed lines represent best fits to the data

consistent with Eq. (14). For the blank glass-ceramic, the fit was performed for for $P < 100$ N (at loads greater than 100 N the strength data show a slight increase above the $P^{-1/3}$ dependence, indicative of lateral-crack influences which reduce the residual stress field [Cook and Roach, 1986; Cook, 2015]). Over this load range the data for the blank material are well described by Eq. (14), consistent with constant toughness [Chantikul *et al.*, 1981]. For the composites, the fits were performed for for $P > 100$ N (at loads less than 100 N the strength data show slight decreases below the $P^{-1/3}$ dependence, indicative of small toughness decreases [Cook, 2015]). Over this load range the data for the composites are also well described by Eq. (14), consistent with constant toughness. Table 2 gives the means and standard deviations of the best fit S parameters describing the dashed lines. Solid symbols represent the means and standard deviations of the intrinsic strengths. Table 2 gives the means and standard deviations of the σ_f and P_f parameters describing the solid symbols. Using these values, the solid lines in Fig. 11 represent mean best fits to the entire data ranges of strengths using Eq. (19) and the shaded bands represent standard deviations of these means.

Figure 11. Plots of indentation (open symbols) and intrinsic (solid symbols) strengths of glass ceramic silicon nitride whisker composites as a function of indentation load. Lines and bands represents best fits consistent with indentation flaw dominance at large loads and intrinsic flaw dominance at small loads.

Two major features appear in Fig. 11. The first is that the indentation strengths, and therefore associated S parameters, Table 2, increase with increasing volume fraction of whiskers, indicating increasing toughening. Using the values in Tables 1 and 2 gives the relative inert toughness of the composites $T_{\text{inert}}/T_{\text{inert}}^0$ from Eq. 16 as 1.3 (5 % composite), 1.5 (10 %), and 1.9 (15 %), consistent with those from the reactive environment short-crack measurements of Fig. 8 and the long crack measurements of Fig. 10. The absolute values of the toughness T_{inert} can be approximated by a characteristic value of $\eta = 0.61$ [Cook *et al.*, 1987] leading to the toughness values shown in Table 2. The second major feature in Fig. 11 is that the intrinsic strengths σ_f do not vary appreciably with the volume fraction of whiskers. The combination of the two features leads to a significant increase in the characteristic indentation load P_f with whisker volume fraction. As P_f marks the transition from indentation flaw control to intrinsic flaw control, the increase suggests that additional whiskers increase both the toughness and the intrinsic flaw size in the composites.

The variation of the intrinsic flaw sizes in the materials is investigated further through analysis of the intrinsic strength distributions. Figure 12 shows plots of edf measurements for composite materials. The symbols represent individual strength measurements. The solid lines represent best fits to the measurements using Eq. (20). The dashed line represents a best fit to measurements on the blank glass ceramic [Cook, 2019] and is reproduced as a reference in each sub-plot. The distributions exhibit sigmoidal behavior and, as anticipated from Fig. 11, vary little with whisker volume fraction. The pdfs describing the flaws underlying the strength variations of Fig. 12 were determined using the above analysis and identifying D with the T_{inert} values given in Table 2. Figure 13 shows the resulting crack size pdfs (interpolating the 8 % D value as 1.95 MPa m^{1/2}). Consistent with the single-valued P_f characterization, the more detailed assessment of flaw size distribution in Fig. 13 shows that the flaw sizes controlling intrinsic strengths increase significantly with increasing whisker volume fraction. In all cases, the inferred flaw size distributions extend about a factor of two from the smallest to largest flaw and are skewed towards larger flaws. In the case of blank glass ceramic the flaws are probably surface machining or polishing flaws. In the case of the composites, the flaws are probably associated with the bulk pores shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The flaw sizes in Fig. 13 are probably upper bounds for two reasons: The decrease in toughness with crack length in the composites was not taken into account and the intensifying influence on applied stress adjacent to pores was not taken into account. Nevertheless, the sizes of the flaws inferred from self-consistent application of indentation and intrinsic strength measurements is comparable to those observed.

Figure 12. Plots of intrinsic strength edf measurements for glass ceramic silicon nitride whisker composites. Dashed line shows response of blank glass ceramic. Strength varies little with whisker content.

Figure 13. Plot of intrinsic flaw pdf responses for glass ceramic silicon nitride whisker composites. Flaw size increases significantly with whisker content.

Table 2. Strength and toughness properties of glass ceramic-whisker composites

Property	Volume fraction whiskers, V_f (%)				
	0	5	8	10	15
Indentation Strength Parameter, S (MPa $N^{1/3}$)	242 ± 19	331 ± 26		389 ± 51	482 ± 42
Intrinsic Strength, σ_f (MPa)	266 ± 29	297 ± 25	268 ± 26	243 ± 24	241 ± 21
Intrinsic Load, P_f (N)	0.75 ± 0.30	1.38 ± 0.48		4.1 ± 2.0	8.0 ± 2.9
Toughness, T_{inert} (MPa $m^{1/2}$)	1.40 ± 0.08	1.81 ± 0.11	~1.95	2.09 ± 0.21	2.62 ± 0.18

5. Conclusions

Composites of cordierite glass-ceramics containing silicon nitride whiskers were fabricated by free sintering. The introduction of the whiskers retarded densification of the composites such that for whisker volume fractions greater than 15 vol% significant open porosity along with entangled whisker agglomerates were generated. Material properties that depended on the composite behavior as a whole were well described by volume-averaged estimates. In particular, Young's modulus was invariant and exhibited a trade-off in whisker addition between the influence of stiff whiskers and the counter-acting effects of increased porosity generated by the whiskers on sintering. Material properties that depended on the local response of a constituent element and for which the response mechanism was altered (hardness, toughness, and strength) were not well describe by volume-based estimates. Hardness exhibited a significant decrease on whisker addition and was dominated by the enhanced porosity. Toughness exhibited a significant increase on whisker addition, although this increase was not reflected in the strength. In each case, the composites responded differently from the bulk constituents: pore collapse controlled the contact deformation leading to the softening; whisker pullout controlled the crack propagation leading to the toughening; and, porous whisker entanglements increased the dominant flaw size, counteracting the toughening, leading to an invariance in the strength with the volume fraction of whiskers added. Quantitatively, toughness increased monotonically with whisker volume fraction to give a steady-state toughness at 15 vol% of approximately 2.6 MPa $m^{1/2}$, compared with that of the blank glass-ceramic of 1.4 MPa $m^{1/2}$.

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References

- Anstis GR, Chantikul P, Lawn BR, Marshall DB (1981) A critical evaluation of indentation techniques for measuring fracture toughness: I, Direct crack measurements. *J Am Ceram Soc* 64:533–538.
- Braun LM, Bennison SJ, Lawn BR (1992) Objective evaluation of short-crack toughness curves using indentation flaws: Case study on alumina-based ceramics. *J Am Ceram Soc* 75:3049-3057.
- Chantikul P, Anstis GR, Lawn BR, Marshall DB (1981) A critical evaluation of indentation techniques for measuring fracture toughness: II, Strength method. *J Am Ceram Soc* 64:539–543.
- Chao LY, Shetty DK (1992) Extreme-value statistics analysis of fracture strengths of a sintered silicon nitride failing from pores. *J Am Ceram Soc* 75:2116-2124.
- Cook RF (2015) Multi-scale effects in the strength of ceramics. *J Am Ceram Soc* 98:2933–2947.
- Cook RF (2018a) Model for instrumented indentation of brittle open-cell foam. *MRS Comm* 8:1267-1273.
- Cook RF (2018b) A simple method for short-term mechanical reliability predictions for ceramics in reactive environments. *J Am Ceram Soc* 101:2727-2731.
- Cook RF (2020a) A critical evaluation of indentation crack lengths in air. *J Am Ceram Soc* 103:2278–229.
- Cook RF (2020b) Refinement and application of a modified indentation toughness technique. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4036754>.
- Cook RF (2020c) Single particle strength distributions: Heavy tails and extreme values. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4024618>.
- Cook RF, DelRio FW (2019a) Material flaw populations and component strength distributions in the context of the Weibull function. *Exp Mechanics* 59:279-293.
- Cook RF, DelRio FW (2019b) Determination of ceramic flaw populations from component strengths. *J Am Ceram Soc* 102:4794-4808.
- Cook RF, DelRio FW, Boyce BL (2019) Predicting strength distributions of MEMS structures using flaw size and spatial density. *Microsystems & Nanoengineering* 5:49.

- Cook RF, Fairbanks CJ, Lawn BR, Mai Y-W (1987) Crack resistance by interfacial bridging: Its role in determining strength characteristics. *J Mater Res* 2:345-356.
- Cook RF, Lawn BR (1983) A modified indentation toughness technique. *J Am Ceram Soc* 66:C200-C201.
- Cook RF, Pharr GM (1990) Direct observation and analysis of indentation cracking in glasses and ceramics. *J Am Ceram Soc* 73:787-817.
- Cook RF, Roach DH (1986) The effect of lateral crack growth on the strength of contact flaws in brittle materials. *J Mater Res* 1:589-600.
- DelRio FW, Boyce BL, Benzing JT, Friedman LH, Cook RF (2020) Shoulder fillet effects in strength distributions of microelectromechanical system components. *J Micromech Microeng* 30:125013.
- Homeny J, Neergaard LJ, Karasek KR, Donner JT, Bradley SA (1990) Characterisation of β -silicon nitride whiskers. *J Am Ceram Soc* 73:102-105.
- Hughey MP, Morris DJ, Cook RF, Bozeman SP, Kelly BL, Chakravarty SLN, Harkens DP, Stearns LC (2004) Four-point bend adhesion measurements of copper and permalloy systems. *Engin Fracture Mech* 71/2:245-261.
- Knickerbocker JU (1992) Overview of the glass-ceramic/copper substrate-A high performance multilayer package for the 1990s. *Am Ceram Soc Bull* 71:1393-1401.
- Knickerbocker SH, Kumar AH, Herron LW (1993) Cordierite glass-ceramics for multilayer ceramic packaging. *Am Ceram Soc Bull* 72:90-95.
- Kovar D, Bennison SJ, Readey MJ (2000). Crack stability and strength variability in alumina ceramics with rising toughness-curve behavior. *Acta mater* 48:565-578.
- Lawn BR, Cook RF (2012) Probing material properties with sharp indenters: A retrospective. *J Mater Sci* 47:1-22.
- Lawn BR, Marshall DB, Chantikul, Anstis GR (1980) Indentation fracture: Applications in the assessment of strength of materials. *J Aust Ceram Soc* 16:4-9.
- Marshall DB (1980) An improved biaxial flexure test for ceramics. *Am Ceram Soc Bull* 59:551-553.
- Marshall DB, Cook RF, Padture N, Oyen ML, Pajares A, Bradby J, Reimanis I, Tandon R, Page T, Pharr GM, Lawn BR (2015) The case for indentation as an enduring and exploratory characterization tool. *J Am Ceram Soc* 98:2671-2680.

Tabor D The Hardness of Metals, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1951.

Tandon R, Cook RF (1993) Indentation crack initiation and propagation in tempered glass. J Am Ceram Soc 76:85-889.

Thurn J, Morris DJ, Cook RF (2002) Depth-sensing indentation at macroscopic dimensions. J Mater Res 17:2679-2690.

Tummala RR (1991) Ceramic and glass-ceramic packaging in the 1990s. J Am Ceram Soc 74:895-908.